

FINLAND

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MANAGEMENT, ECONOMICS & SOCIAL SCIENCE

A MASTERPIECE OF KHOREZM ARCHITECTURE**Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnudbek ugli****Teacher at Mamun university****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16593890>****Introduction.**

Islam Khoja Madrasah is located in the Ichan Kala area of the city of Khiva and is one of the most famous architectural monuments of Uzbekistan. This madrasah was built at the beginning of the 20th century, in 1908-1910, by Said Islam Khoja, the prime minister and father-in-law of the Khiva Khan Asfandiyorkhan. He played an important role in the social and cultural life of Khiva in his time. The architectural structure, historical significance and current condition of the madrasah make this structure worthy of special appreciation not only as a religious center, but also as a national heritage.

Islam Khoja Madrasah was built in the last years of the Khiva Khanate. The construction work was supervised by the master Khudoybergan Khoji. During the reign of Asfandiyorkhan, he was the prime minister, governed the southern part of the khanate and managed relations with foreign countries. For his services in the administration of the khanate, he was awarded the title of “Vaziri Akbar” in 1910. He actively participated in the development of a decree on reforms in the khanate. In order to alleviate the situation of peasants in Khorezm, which was based on irrigated agriculture, he tried to reduce the land tax. Baked bricks, cement, and oil were used in the construction of the architectural monument. The main task of the madrasah was to provide religious and secular knowledge to Muslim youth.

Islam Khoja was one of the progressive figures of his time and made a great contribution to the development of the modern infrastructure of Khiva. He led the construction of hospitals, post and telegraph buildings, and bridges in the city. At the same time, the development of the religious and educational sphere was also in the focus of his attention.

The main structure of the Islam Khoja madrasah is two-story, and a special mosque was also built on the right side of the entrance. The exterior and decoration of the madrasah, which is connected to the main facade with a minaret, do not differ much from other

madrasahs in Khiva. The side wings of the roof are decorated with two-story porches and flower arrangements at the corners. The tops of the porches are decorated with borders and shirkor tiles. There is no decoration on the walls of the courtyard. The courtyard (23x20) is surrounded by 42 small one-story rooms. There is an ayvan on the second floor of the main building facing the courtyard. The mosque in the southeast of the madrasah is domed, and the mihrab is decorated with tiles and ganchkori patterns. The domed room located in the southeast corner of the mosque is distinguished by its mihrab, which is decorated with tiles and ganchkori patterns. The interior of the mosque is closed in the form of a large domed room, typical of the Khiva school of art. A beautiful landscape is created under the dome in the corner located on the south side of the mosque and on the mihrab using shirkor and ganchkori decorations. Islam Khoja allocated 14,451 tala of land from his estate as a foundation for the construction of the madrasah.

The most striking part of the madrasah is its minaret. The Islam Khoja minaret is the tallest structure in Khiva, with a height of 56.6 meters. The exterior of the minaret is decorated with blue and green tiles, which makes it visible from afar. The architect Khudoybergan Khoji, the artists Eshmuhammad Khudoyberdiev, Bolta Voisov and others took part in the construction of the Islam Khoja madrasah and its minaret. Those who want to admire the city from the top of the minaret must climb one hundred and seventy-five steep steps of the spiral staircase, and the only lifting device here is your feet. Do not be surprised if sometimes you have to put your hands on the high stone steps and climb. But on the other hand, the reward for you will be a magnificent panorama of the Eastern city, a city from a fairy tale, and you will become a person who has seen with his own eyes Khiva, dimly flickering in the distance and sand ridges floating in the hot marewa. Around the minaret, countless houses with flat roofs and closed courtyards, domes and mosques and minarets burning in the sun, a winding chain of ancient fortress walls looms in the distance. It is no exaggeration to say that this minaret has become a symbol of Khiva.

For many years, the architectural structure served as a place for the muezzin to call to prayer, and in recent years it has also been used for military purposes - as an observation post. The architectural structure was renovated several times before and after independence and was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. In connection with the 2500th

anniversary of the city of Khiva, the Islam Khoja complex was renovated, along with other architectural monuments in the city of Khiva. The minaret has preserved its legendary appearance in the historical center of the city of Ichan Kala, and in 1990, the “Ichan Kala” in Khiva was included in the list of World Cultural Heritage.

At the same time, the historical and cultural significance of the Islam Khoja madrasah is that in its time it functioned not only as a place of religious education, but also as a socio-educational center. Many religious scholars and intellectuals have graduated from this madrasah. Islam Khoja left a name in history as a person who, through his work, was able to combine Islamic values with modernity.

The modern significance of the madrasa is also great. Currently, this madrasa operates as the "Khorezm Museum of Applied Arts". The museum houses woodcarvings, metalwork, and other similar crafts.

References:

1. Ismailov, T. (2025). Centers Of Enlightenment During The Khiva Khanate. Current Approaches And New Research In Modern Sciences (T. 4, Выпуск 7, сс. 175–176).
2. Ismailov, T. (2025). Architectural monuments of the ancient city of Khiva. International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science, 3(2), 23–24.
3. Ismailov, T. (2022, November). The Fort That Speaks From The Past. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol.1, No.31, pp.1822).
4. Ismailov, T. (2024). Palace Of The Khorezmshakh. Models and methods in modern science, 3(3), 5-7.
5. Ismailov, T. (2024). Ko’hna va hamisha navqiron shahar. Молодые ученые, 2(2), 71-72.
6. Ismailov, T. (2023). Embossed Khiva Pillars. Current approaches and new research in Modern sciences, 2(4), 63-66.
7. Ismailov, T. (2024). Monument Sof Ancient Khorezm. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(4), 175-176.